

Germination Characteristics of *Parinari curatellifolia* Planch. Ex Benth, *Vitex doniana* Sweet and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* (Lam) Watermann Seeds

Tiga Neya^{1*}, Edhit Daboue¹, Oble Neya¹ and Issaka Ouedraogo²

¹Centre National des Semences Forestières Ouagadougou, 03 BP 6282 Ouagadougou 03, Burkina Faso.

²Laboratory of Plant Biology and Ecology, Department of Plant Biology and Physiology, UFR/SVT, University of Ouagadougou, 03 BP 7021 Ouagadougou 03, Burkina Faso.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Author TN designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors ON and ED managed the analyses of the study. Author IO managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: 10.9734/ARRB/2017/32209

Editor(s):

- (1) Jin-Zhi Zhang, College of Horticulture and Forestry Science, Huazhong Agricultural University, China.
(2) George Perry, Dean and Professor of Biology, University of Texas at San Antonio, USA.

Reviewers:

- (1) Ibrahim Demir, University of Ankara, Turkey.
(2) Hakan Sevik, Kastamonu University, Turkey.

Complete Peer review History: <http://www.sciencedomain.org/review-history/18572>

Original Research Article

Received 14th February 2017

Accepted 20th March 2017

Published 10th April 2017

ABSTRACT

Germination characteristics studies of seeds of three local species in Burkina Faso namely *Parinari curatellifolia*, *Vitex doniana* and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* have been carried out. The aim of this study was to carry out the appropriate pre-treatment and temperature which give the best percentage of seed germination for these three locales species. For that the seed were placed in different temperature 15°C; 20°C; 25°C; 30°C; 35°C and 19 pre-treatment from Soaking in water x hours; Scalding, Cooking x minute, Soaking of sulfuric acid x minute, scarification and decorticating were applied for all seeds used for this study's. For temperature test, only *Parinaria curatellifolia* seeds are germinated at 35°C with 13%. Sulphuric acid pre-treatments during 60 mn for *Vitex*

*Corresponding author: E-mail: neyatiga@gmail.com;

doniana seeds and 5 mn for *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* seeds gave the highest germination percentages in the laboratory, respectively 40% and 62%. None of the numerous pre-treatments applied to the seeds of *Parinari curatellifolia*, led to successful germination. While, for *Vitex doniana* and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* seeds we can conclude that their seeds are dealing with a physical dormancy that is overcome by chemical scarification, seeds of *Parinari curatellifolia* have a deeper dormancy, which may be physiological or combined (physical and physiological).

Keywords: Germination; *Parinari curatellifolia*; *Vitex doniana*; *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conservation of plant resources in general and woody species in particular, for sustainable development and poverty alleviation, continues to be a concern for decision makers and local populations in Burkina Faso [1]. For several decades, Burkina Faso, like other Sahelian countries, has been experiencing a gradual degradation of its natural ecosystems. This degradation due to the vagaries of climate is increased by exponential growth of population whose needs are increasingly increasing and diversified [2]. Natural resources, overexploited, then become scarce, which shows among other things the interest of the forest and the tree for humanity.

Large-scale planting, domestication of local species, management and conservation of natural forests, adherence to national and international programs and conventions for biodiversity conservation etc., are all actions that Burkina Faso, like other Sahelian countries, leads to overcome adversity of nature. However, it must be recognized that plantations and domestication of local species are confronted with sociocultural constraints and insufficient of scientific knowledge about the ecology of regeneration of indigenous species [3]. In Burkina Faso, most plantations are based on seedlings grown in nurseries [4]. In addition, 90% of artificial woodlots in Burkina Faso (BF) are generally based on forest trees seeds used either as direct seedlings or as silvicultural plants [5]. The success of reforestation based on given seed requires a good knowledge of physiology of plant material used. In addition, a good knowledge of seed biology, physiology, constraints on germination and conservation are an essential prerequisite for rational, sustainable use and enhanced valorisation of local species [6].

Parinari curatellifolia, *Vitex doniana*, and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* are endangered

species. These threats are inherent in their multiple uses. Indeed, these species are used in several areas including food, handicrafts and traditional medicine. The roots, barks (stem and root) and leaves are used in the curative treatment of gastric diseases, hemorrhoids, rheumatism, sickle cell anemia, malaria, gonorrhoea, hernias, dental caries, panaris, Snakes bites, etc. The bark of *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* would be an excellent vasodilator. The therapeutic properties of the plant are due to the richness of the latter in highly diversified molecules (flavonoids, saponosides, coumarins, nitrogen bases, alkaloids, tripterpenoids etc [7].

The fruits of *Vitex doniana* and *Parinari curatellifolia* are edible and are locally marketed [8]. Young leaves of *Vitex doniana* are used as vegetables during the lean season [9]. The leaves, roots, bark of *Parinari curatellifolia* and *Vitex doniana* are used in traditional medicine [10,11,12,13]. *Parinari curatellifolia* in particular would seem to have extraordinary socio-economic interests [14]. Indeed, according to Hiene and Eckman cited by [15] the pulp of *Parinari curatellifolia* is edible and can be processed into jam while oil extracted from oilseeds is used in many sectors of economy (soap, cosmetics, ink, painting ...). *Parinari curatellifolia* and *Vitex doniana*, in addition to the edibility of its fruit, are a "highly" agroforestry species [15,16,17]. These species contribute to the fertilization of soils and the production of timber and firewood. Burkina Faso will have "an inestimable lack has won" if no study is oriented in the domestication of these plants [15]. This domestication necessarily involves knowledge of the biology of seeds of these species.

As such, there are no stands of *Vitex doniana* and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides*, except for clusters of a few feet per location and in some (specific) regions of the country. These species, which breed mainly by the seeds, are therefore

threatened with extinction. In addition, very little information is available on the seeds of these species. The work of Sanon et al. [18] on *Parinari curatellifolia* and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* showed that the initial germination rates of 0% and 2% respectively are essentially due to problems of dormancy and / or seed immaturity.

The purpose of this study is to determine the characteristic of germination of these species.

But specifically it was to determine the appropriate temperature and pre-treatment to be applied in order to obtain the best germination rate of seeds. Hypothesis were, fruit maturity and temperature have an impact of seed germination and there is an appropriate pre-treatment for each trees species seeds.

2. MATERIELS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The seeds of all the three species have been used for the study's purpose (Plates 1, 2, 3).

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Germination test

The germination tests were done in the laboratory of National Trees Seeds Centre Ouagadougou (CNSF). Seedlings were carried out on screened, sterilized and moistened river sand. For each trial, the number of repetitions and the number of seeds per replication varied according to species. For both *Parinari curatellifolia* and *Vitex doniana*, two (2)

Photo 1. Brown and hard green fruits (immature stage)

Photo 2. Oranges harvested (mature stage)

Photo 3. Fruit brown picked (mature stage)

Photo 4. Seeds from fruits in the mature stage

Plate 1. Photos of fruits of *Parinari curatellifolia* harvested at different stages of maturity and seeds extracted from mature fruits

Photo 5. Green fruits (immature stage)

Photo 6. Green yellow fruits (intermediate stage)

Photo 7. Black fruits (mature stage)

Photo 8. Seeds extracted from mature fruit

Plate 2. Photos of the fruits of the different stages of maturity of *Vitex doniana* harvested and seeds of the species

repetitions of twenty five (25) seeds were used for each trial while for *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* two (2) repetitions of fifty (50) seeds were used for each trial. After seeding the seed boxes have been hermetically sealed to maintain sufficient moisture for germination. They were then placed on the germination benches under the ambient conditions of the CNSF laboratory where the temperature varies between 25 and 30°C.

Germination Survey were conducted each two days. The mean duration of each trial was 6 months for *Parinari curatellifolia* and *Vitex doniana*, and 2 months for *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides*. At the end of each germination test, all non-germinated seeds were systematically dissected to determine the number of: rotten / moldy seeds; hard and / or soaked seeds; empty seeds; infested seeds. These data were taken into account for the

calculation of germination percentage of the sample tested.

2.2.2 Determination of seed germination characteristics and conditions

2.2.2.1 Effect of temperature on germination

The objective of this part of the study was to determine the optimum temperature which allows a good germination (rapid and homogeneous emergence) of the seeds of each of these three species. Thus, for all three species, germination tests were performed in incubators set at different temperatures (15, 25, 30 and 35°C). The boxes containing the seedlings were wrapped in transparent plastic bags to avoid contamination before being placed at different germination temperatures (photo 13). Three repetitions of ten seeds (3 x 10 seeds) were used for all tests. Only seeds from mature fruits of each species were used.

Photo 9. Green fruits (immature stage)

Photo 10. Fruits red green (intermediate stage)

Photo 11. Red fruits (mature stage)

Photo 12. Seeds from mature fruit

Plate 3. Photos of fruits of different stages of maturity of *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* harvested and seeds of the species after preparation

Table 1. List of pre-treatments applied by species

Pretreatment	<i>Parinari curatellifolia</i>	<i>Vitex doniana</i>	<i>Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides</i>
None/Witnesses	x	x	x
TE24H	x	x	x
TE48H	x	x	x
TE96H	x	-	-
Eb+TE 24H	x	x	x
Eb + TE 48H	x	x	x
C1mn + TE 24H	x	x	x
C5mn + TE 24H	x	x	x
C10mn +TE 24H	x	x	x
TA1mn +TE 24H	x	x	x
TA5mn +TE24H	x	x	x
TA10mn +TE24H	x	x	x
TA30mn + TE24H	x	x	x
TA60mn +TE24H	x	x	x
TA120mn +TE24H	x	-	-
TA5H+TE24H	x	-	-
TA24H +TE72H	x	-	-
scarification	x	x	x
Decorticating	-	x	-

- TExH: Soaking in water x hours
- Eb: Scalding
- Cxmn: Cooking x minute (s)
- TAxmn: Soaking with sulfuric acid x minute (s)

Photo 13. View of seed germination tests of *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* in an adjustable temperature incubator

2.2.2.2 Comparative pretreatment tests

Pretreatment is by definition the treatment (s) carried out before, during or after storage,

which allows the elimination of seed dormancy [19].

The seed of *Parinari curatellifolia* as well as that of *Vitex doniana* is surrounded by a strongly sclerified hard endocarp. One can already suspect that they have a tegumentary dormancy. As regards the seed of *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides*, which is relatively small but oily in size. Its high oil content could have a negative effect on seed imbibition. The objective of comparative pretreatment trials is to determine the most efficient treatment to apply to the seeds of these three species in order to accelerate and improve germination and to obtain a homogeneous seedling emergence. The pretreatment tests were carried out on the seed lots from the mature fruits of each species. Particular attention was paid to the pretreatment parameters, ie the duration of the pretreatment, the amount of acid used (1/3 of the seed volume), the way in which the seeds are stirred

Photo 14. Scarification of *P. curatellifolia* nuts in pruning shears

Photo 15. Scarification of *P. curatellifolia* nuts with ax and hammer

Photo 16. Scalded of *P. curatellifolia* nuts

Photo 17. Scarifying *Z. zanthoxyloides* seeds to the electric burner

Photo 18. Decorticating of *V. doniana* nuts

Photo 19. Fully Shelled *V. doniana* Seeds

Plate 4. Photos of scarification and husking sessions of *P. curatellifolia*, *V. doniana* and *Z. zanthoxyloides* seeds

in the acid in order to make testing more reliable. The thus pretreated seeds were sown due to three replicates of ten seeds per pretreatment for *Vitex doniana* and *Parinari curatellifolia*; Three repetitions of twenty-five (25) seeds for *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides*. The pretreatments were chosen taking into account the structure of the seed coat, and therefore according to the species. Table 1 lists the pretreatments used for each species.

In addition to the pretreatments indicated in Table 1, the seeds of *Vitex doniana* were fully husked and germinated in the sand and on the agar. Also, for *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides*, laboratory germination tests were duplicated in nursery tests for all pretreatments applied.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Temperature Effect on Seeds Germination

For the three-species considered, this study was carried out on seeds from ripe fruit. Five (5) germination temperatures were tested: 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35°C. To achieve these germination temperatures, adjustable temperature incubators were used. The results are shown in Table 2. It is important to note that no pretreatment has been applied to the seed of the different species prior to planting.

For all the temperatures tested and for all species studied, only the seeds of *Parinari curatellifolia* germinated at 35°C. Out of a total of 30 seeds sown, four seeds germinated after 5 months 25 days of sowing, giving a germination percentage of 13.33%. For *Vitex doniana* and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides*, the absence of germination does not necessarily mean that these temperatures do not correspond to the optimal germination temperatures of these species, as these two species apparently show dormancy. It would be appropriate, from our point of view, to first raise this dormancy in order to better appreciate the effect of temperature on the germination of the seeds.

It is recalled that neither fresh nor dried seeds of *Parinari curatellifolia* germinated during the study of desiccation tolerance of seed of the species. The germination rate obtained at 35°C. (Photo 20), even if it remains low, suggests the probable optimal temperature of seed germination of this species, which may be different from that of 20-30°C generally obtained for the germination of

seeds of tropical trees [20,21,1]. Given that we have not tested germination temperatures above 35°C, it is very difficult to conclude that the optimum germination temperature of the seeds of *Parinari curatellifolia* is 35°C. Nevertheless this result would not be free from suspicion about the presence of a physiological dormancy in the seed of this species which is raised by the humid heat.

Photo 20. Young shoots of *Parinari curatellifolia* obtained during germination tests at 35°C

3.2 Comparative Pretreatment Tests

In total, nineteen different pretreatments were tested on the seeds of the three species studied. However, the number varied from one species to another. As a reminder, this part of the study was carried out on the seeds from the ripe fruits of each of the three species. *Parinari curatellifolia* eighteen pretreatments were tested on seed of this species. Of the eighteen, only mechanical scarification resulted in a 2% germination rate after six (6) months of sowing. The germination rate was zero with all the other seven pretreatments. We recall that the tests were carried out on freshly prepared seeds. This result shows that the poor germination of dried *Parinari curatellifolia* seeds is not due to drying. This confirms, in our opinion, the hypothesis of the existence of a dormancy. This dormancy could be integumentary since the scarification made it possible to raise it even if the germination remains weak.

These results can be explained on the one hand by an accentuated integumentary dormancy due to the toughness of the tegument. Indeed, the seed of *Parinari curatellifolia* consists of one to two nuts (Plate 5, Photo 21)

surrounded by a very hard shell lined with a hairy inner envelope (Plate 5, Photo 22). This double protection can delay the humidification of the embryo and subsequently the emergence of the radicle.

These results are comparable to those of [18] on seeds of the same species. In fact, the work of the latter had led to the conclusion that the seeds of *Parinari curatellifolia* did not germinate either

in fresh or dry state and consequently showed a deep and severe dormancy

3.2.1 *Vitex doniana*

Fifteen different pretreatments were applied to the seeds of *Vitex doniana*. The germination rate was zero for all the pretreatments except three of them. The results for these three pretreatments are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Table 2. Germination rate of the specieses seeds following the used temperature

Temperature (°C)	Germination (%)		
	<i>P. curatellifolia</i>	<i>V. doniana</i>	<i>Z. zanthoxyloides</i>
15	0	0	0
20	0	0	0
25	0	0	0
30	0	0	0
35	13,33	0	0

Photo 21. longitudinal section de *P. curatellifolia* nut.

Photo 22. Amende extraite de la noix de *P. curatellifolia*

Plate 5. Photos of the longitudinal section of a seed and nut of *Parinari curatellifolia*

Fig. 1. Percentage of germination of seeds of *Vitex doniana* following the treatment

The pre-treatments which allowed the seeds to germinate are dipping in acid for 30 and 60 minutes and total dehulling with respective germination rates of 17; 40 and 75%. This suggests that the seeds of *Vitex doniana* have a dormancy of integumentary type probably due to the thickness of the envelope that protects the seed. Under the corrosive action of concentrated sulfuric acid (97%), the shell is eaten away, which facilitates the imbibition of the cotyledons and triggers the germination process. The hulling, by removing the seed from its hull, improves both the speed and the percentage of germination. Indeed, shelled seeds reached the germination percentage of only 75% after two days of sowing. This technique could therefore be recommended for a rapid and homogenous emergence of *Vitex doniana* seedlings. Our results are similar to those of [22], who described the mechanism of germination stresses imposed by the *Lannea microcarpa* seed endocarp.

3.2.2 *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides*

Due to the size and structure of the seeds of this species, acid treatment was limited to a maximum duration of 10 min. In total, fourteen different pretreatments were applied to the seeds of this species. Of the fourteen pretreatments tested, only five had a positive effect on seed germination. These pretreatments are: TE 24H and TE48H, TA1mn, TA5mn and TA10mn. The results obtained are illustrated in Fig. 2. We

recall that for this species, the seedlings in the laboratory were replicated in the nursery.

As shown in Fig. 2, seeds soaked in water for 24 and 48 hours germinated in nurseries with respective rates of 12 and 5%. The same seeds sown in the laboratory did not germinate after two months of sowing. Acid treatment seems to be the one that most improves the germination of *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* seeds. The germination rates obtained in the laboratory are 25; 62 and 13% respectively for seeds soaked in acid for one, five and ten minutes. The same seeds sown in nurseries germinated at respective rates of 41; 72 and 48%. Clearly, as shown in Plate 6, *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* seeds germinate better in the nursery than in the laboratory. This marked improvement in seed germination in the nursery could be due either to the substrat difference. In fact, nursery seeding took place in a substrat consisting of a mixture of soil, sand and manure in the respective proportions of 3, 1 and 1.

We retain from this test that soaking in acid and even simple soaking in water at defined durations constitute treatments capable of inducing the germination of the seeds of *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides*. This means that the dormancy predicted by the results of the dessiccation tolerance test may be of the integumentary type. These results seem to be contradictory to those obtained by [18], whose investigations led to the

Fig. 2. Percentage of germination of the seeds of *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* according to the type of pre-treatment and the place of seeding

Photo 23. Seeding device in the shade

Photo 24. Germination of acid pretreated seeds after 38 days of seeding in nursery

Photo 25. Young shoots of *Zanthoxylum* after 36 days of planting in the laboratory (RT 5 mn)

Photo 26. Vegetative state of a few germinated seeds en pépinière et repiqués

Plate 6. *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* seedlings in nursery and laboratory

conclusion that the low percentage of germination of *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* seeds during desiccation was related to physiological dormancy and that to obtain a Germination percentage of the order of 37%, the seeds should be preserved at 4°C. and for 9 months. It can already be considered that the treatment of seeds with concentrated sulfuric acid in the period between 5 and 10 minutes may be suitable for a rapid and homogeneous emergence of *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* seedlings. The study could, however, be further studied by considering the time interval between 1 and 10 minutes in order to determine more precisely the most efficient pretreatment to be applied to the seeds of this species. Also, the success of any plant propagation program, among other things, hinges on a continuous supply of high quality seeds for the production of the desired quantity of seedlings in nurseries or for successful stand establishment by direct

sowing out in the field. Seed quality is a multiple concept encompassing the physical, physiological, genetic, pathological and entomological attributes that affect seed lot performance. And also, seed germination is the most important seed quality feature [23,24,25,26,27].

4. CONCLUSION

At the end of this part of our study we can draw the following conclusions: *Parinari curatellifolia* seeds germinate better at 35°C than in the 20-30°C range often recommended for the germination of tropical seeds. This temperature could be considered the optimum germination temperature of this species. The fresh seeds of the three species studied did not germinate, so the seeds of *Vitex doniana* and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* do not germinate in the temperature range of 15-35°C. However, when

they are pretreated in particular by physical scarification or with acid, a substantial improvement in their germination rate is obtained. For seeds of *Parinari curatellifolia*, the germination rate was still zero even after mechanical scarification. After that, some other techniques must be trying for germination. For example hormone application or combined techniques can be trying. Some researches show that this techniques can be increase the seed germination ratio [28,29]. It can thus be said that the seeds of *Vitex doniana* and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* have an integumentary dormancy whereas those of *Parinari curatellifolia* have a physiological dormancy even combined (physical and physiological).

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Neya O. Conservation of tree seeds from tropical dry-lands. PhD Thesis, Wageningen University and Research Centre. Wageningen, The Netherlands. 2006;159.
2. FAO. Responding to agricultural and food insecurity challenges mobilizing Africa to implement Nepad Programmes FAO. Maputo, Mozambique; 2003.
3. Bationo BA. Régénération naturelles et fonctionnement des espèces ligneuses dans la forêt classée de Nazinon (Burkina Faso): *Detarium microcarpum* (Guill.et Perr)., *Azelia africana* (Sm)., *Isobertinia doka* (Craib et Stapf)., *Piliostigma thonningii* de Ouagadougou. 2002;165. French
4. Gaméné CS. Contribution à la maîtrise des méthodes simples de prétraitements et de conservation des semences de quelques espèces ligneuses récoltées au Burkina Faso. Mémoire de fin d'études IDR/UO. 1987;96. French
5. Sacandé M. Influence de la lumière et de la température sur la germination des graines de neuf espèces forestières récoltées au Burkina Faso. CNSF. 1993;180-191. French
6. Neya O. Etude des stades de développement des fruits de Neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss). Mémoire de fin d'étude IDR. 1999;66. French
7. Nacoulma O. Plantes médicinales et pratiques médicales traditionnelles au Burkina Faso: Cas du plateau central. Thèse de doctorat, tome II; UO. 1996;285. French
8. Adetoro KO, Bolanle JD, Abdullahi SB, Ahmed OA. *In vivo* antioxidant effect of aqueous root bark, stem bark and leaves extracts of *Vitex doniana* in CCl₄ induced liver damage rats. Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine. 2013;3(5):395-400.
9. Ouattara A, Coulibaly A, Adima AA, Ouattara K. Exploration of the antistaphylococcic activity of *Vitex doniana* (Verbenaceae) stem bark extracts. Academic Journal of Pharmacy. 2013;2(2): 94-100.
10. Arbonnier M. Arbres, arbustes et lianes de zones sèches d'Afrique de l'Ouest. CIRAD.MNHN. IUCN. 2002;573. French
11. Sanogo R, Karadji Avarga Halimatou H, Demebele O, Diallo R. Activité diurétique et sadiurétique d'une recette en médecine traditionnelle pour le traitement de l'hypertension artérielle. Mali Médical. 2009;23(4):1-6. French
12. Amegbor K, Metowogo K, Eklu-Gadegboku K, Agbonon A, Aklikokou KA, Napo-Koura G, et al. Preliminary evaluation of the wound healing effect of *Vitex doniana* sweet (Verbenaceae) in mice. African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines. 2012;9(4):584-590.
13. Kranjac-Berisavljevic G, Gandaa BZ. Importance of bush grape (*Vitex* spp.) as food and medicinal plant to the Dagarti speaking people of the Upper West Region of Northern Ghana. Acta Horticulturae. 2013;979:669-673.
14. Wala K, Guelly AK, Batawila K, Dourma M, Sinsin B, Akpagana K. Traditional agroforestry systems in Togo: Variability according to latitude and local communities. IUFRO World Series. 2009;23:21-27.
15. Boussim JI, Lykke AM, Nombé I, Nielsen I, Guinko S. Homme plantes et environnement au sahel occidental, acte de l'atelier de Fada N'gourma (Burkina Faso). 2004;333. French
16. Yaméogo G, Yélémo B, Traoré D. Pratique et perception paysannes dans la création de parc agroforestier dans le terroir de Vipalogo (Burkina Faso). BASE [En ligne]. 2005;9:241-248. French Available:<http://popups.ulg.ac.be/1780-4507/index.php?id=1404>

17. Faye MD, Weber JC, Mounkoro B, Dakouo JM. Contribution of parkland trees to village livelihoods: A case study from Mali. *Development in Practice*. 2010;20:428-434.
18. Sanon DM, Gaméné CS, Sacandé M, Neya O. Desiccation and storage of *Kigelia africana*, *Lophira lanceolata*, *Parinari curatellifolia* and *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* seeds from Burkina Faso. *Comparative Storage Biology of Tropical Tree Seeds*, Sacandé M, Joker D, Dulloo ME, Thomsen KA, (eds): International Plant Genetic Resources Institute, Rome, Italy. 2004;16-29.
19. Gaméné CS. Conservation des semences orthodoxes, intermédiaires et récalcitrantes. IPGRI. in *Vers une approche régionale des ressources génétiques forestières en Afrique Sub-saharienne*. Acte du premier atelier régional formation sur la conservation et l'utilisation durable des ressources génétiques forestières en Afrique de l'Ouest, Afrique Centrale et Madagascar, 16-27 mai 1998, CNSF. Ouagadougou Burkina Faso. A.S. Ouédraogo et J.M. Boffa (Eds). IPGRI Rome, Italie. 1998;162-169. French
20. Sacandé M, Golovina EA, Van AC, Hoekstra FA. Viability loss of neem (*Azadirachta indica*) seed associated with membrane phase behaviour. *Journal of Experimental Botany*. 2001;51:635-643.
21. Gaméné CS, Eriksen NE. Storage behaviour of *Khaya senegalensis* seed from Burkina Faso. *Comparative storage biology of tropical tree seeds*. Sacandé M, Joker D, Dulloo ME, Thomsen KA, (ed): International Plant Genetic Resources Institute, Rome, Italy. 2004;9-15.
22. Neya O, Hoekstra FA, Golovina EA. Mechanism of endocarp-imposed constraints of germination of *Lannea microcarpa* seeds. *Seed Science Research*. 2008;18:13-24.
23. Sevik H. The differences among populations in Scotch pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) seed stands of Western Black Sea region M.Sc Thesis, Gazi University Inst. Sci. Technol. 2005;60.
24. Sevik H, Yahyaoglu Z, Turna I. Determination of genetic variation between populations of *Abies nordmanniana* subsp. *bornmulleriana* Mattf according to some seed characteristics, genetic diversity in plants, ISBN 978-953-51-0185-7, InTech, 2012;Chapter 12:231-248.
25. Sevik H, Topacoglu O. Variation and inheritance pattern in cone and seed characteristics of Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) for evaluation of genetic diversity. *Journal of Environmental Biology*. 2015;36(5):1125-1130.
26. Sevik H, Guney K. Effects of IAA, IBA, NAA, and GA3 on rooting and morphological features of *Melissa officinalis* L. stem cuttings. *The Scientific World Journal*; 2013.
27. Sevik H, Cetin M. Effects of some hormone applications on germination and morphological characters of endangered plant species *Lilium artvinense* L. Onion scales. *Bulgarian Chemical Communications*. 2016;48(2):256-260.
28. Sevik H, Guney K, Topacoglu O, Unal C. The influences of rooting media and hormone applications on rooting percentage and some root characters in *Schefflera arboricola*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science Invention*. 2015;4(2):25-29.
29. Topacoglu O, Sevik H, Guney K, Unal C, Akkuzu E, Sivacioglu A. Effect of rooting hormones on the rooting capability of *Ficus benjamina* L. Cuttings. *Şumarski List*. 2016;140(1-2):39-44.

© 2017 Neya et al.; This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Peer-review history:
 The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:
<http://sciencedomain.org/review-history/18572>